

STUDY PROTOCOL

Project Title: Construct and Concurrent Validity of the Test of Infants' Daily Living Activities (Test of IDLA)

Ethical Approval Reference: Resolution no. 15/52

Approval Body: Thematic Team for Ethics in Scientific Research of Physiotherapists at the Polish Chamber of Physiotherapists

Basis of Protocol: This document details the methodology and statistical analysis plan implemented in accordance with the ethical approval granted on June 29, 2022.

BACKGROUND AND RATIONALE

Functional diagnostics is a crucial aspect of assessing psychomotor development in infants. Early detection and accurate analysis of developmental disorders—both quantitative and qualitative—provide an opportunity to correct abnormalities and rapidly implement therapeutic interventions. Most standardized tools for assessing motor development (e.g., AIMS, Bayley Scales) were developed in English-speaking countries. This creates challenges for clinical practice in Poland, including difficulties in understanding standardization rules or differences arising from unauthorized translations. Therefore, there is a significant need for a validated tool in the Polish language that offers high reliability, validity, and sensitivity. To address this, the *Test of Infants' Daily Living Activities (IDLA)* was developed based on the guidelines of the National Council of Physiotherapists. The purpose of this study is to conduct a comparative validation of the IDLA against a recognized gold standard, the Alberta Infant Motor Scale (AIMS).

STUDY OBJECTIVES

The primary objective of this study is to determine the psychometric properties of the Test of IDLA using a scientific methodology. **Specific Objectives:**

1. To assess the **construct validity** of the Test of IDLA (Postural Control and Motor Control domains).
2. To demonstrate the **concurrent validity** of the Test of IDLA in relation to the Alberta Infant Motor Scale (AIMS).
3. To determine the diagnostic accuracy (Sensitivity, Specificity, AUC) and optimal cut-off points for the IDLA.

METHODS

1. Study Design

This is an observational, cross-sectional validation study. The data collection is part of a broader research project initiated in 2023.

2. Setting

The study will be conducted at the "Fizjosesomed" physiotherapy practice in Opole, Poland.

3. Participants

- **Target Population:**

Infants referred for early physiotherapeutic intervention.

- **Planned Sample Size:**

The initial application estimated 100–150 participants. However, recruitment will be extended to achieve higher statistical power (target >300), verified by G*Power analysis.

- **Inclusion Criteria:**

1. Age between 1 and 18 months.
2. Informed written consent of parents/legal guardians.

- **Exclusion Criteria:**

1. Major congenital anomalies or genetic syndromes.
2. Clinical instability.
3. Recent injuries or surgical procedures.
4. Active infection/inflammation during examination.
5. Lack of parental consent.

4. Procedure

The examination protocol consists of three parts:

- a) **Interview:** Collection of demographic and perinatal data (Apgar score, birth weight, gestational age, delivery type).
- b) **AIMS Assessment (Reference Standard):** Assessment of spontaneous motor activity in four positions (prone, supine, sitting, standing) according to Piper and Darrah's methodology.
- c) **IDLA Assessment (Index Test):** Assessment using the Test of IDLA sheets for Postural Control and Motor Control. Scoring: 0 (unable), 1 (with assistance), 2 (independent).

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS PLAN (SAP)

Data analysis will be performed using **MedCalc® Statistical Software** and **G*Power®**. The significance level is set at.

1. **Descriptive Statistics** Categorical variables will be presented as proportions. Continuous variables will be tested for normality using the **Shapiro-Wilk test**. Non-normally distributed data will be reported as median and interquartile range (IQR).
2. **Validity Analysis**
 - **Construct Validity:** Will be assessed by calculating **Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (rho)** between the Test of IDLA (Activity Indicators) and the AIMS total score. Interpretation: $\rho > 0.7$ indicates a strong correlation.
 - **Concordance:** The relationship between classifications (Low/Normal) on both scales will be tested using the **Chi-square test (χ^2)** and **Cramér's V**.
3. **Diagnostic Accuracy**
 - **ROC Curve Analysis:** Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve analysis will be conducted to determine the Area Under the Curve (AUC) for the IDLA, using AIMS as the reference standard.
 - **Cut-off Point:** The optimal cut-off point for the IDLA Activity Indicator will be determined using the **Pareto optimal criterion**, balancing sensitivity and specificity. Cost ratio assumption: False Negative (FN) cost = 2, False Positive (FP) cost = 1.
 - **Predictive Value:** Logistic regression analysis will be performed to assess the predictive capability of the IDLA score concerning the AIMS outcome.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The study was conducted in strict adherence to the Declaration of Helsinki. Participation was voluntary and anonymous. All parents/legal guardians provided written informed consent prior to inclusion. The study procedures (examination using AIMS and Test of IDLA) were reviewed and authorized by the Thematic Team for Ethics in Scientific Research of Physiotherapists at the Polish Chamber of Physiotherapists (Resolution no. 15/52).